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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Soil as alternative thermal energy supply in very shallow geothermal application: an overview of ITER project

Nowadays renewable energy resources for heating/cooling residential and tertiary buildings and agricultural greenhouses are becoming increasingly important. In this framework, a possible, natural and valid alternative for thermal energy supply is represented by soils. In fact, since 1980 soils have been studied and used also as heat reservoir in geothermal applications, acting as a heat source (in winter) or sink (in summer) coupled mainly with heat pumps. Therefore, it is worthy of interest a better comprehension of how the different soil typologies (i.e.

sand, loamy sand...) affect and are affected by the heat transfer exchange with heat collectors, especially when horizontal ones (very shallow geothermal installations) are adopted. In this study the preliminary results of ITER Project (<http://iter-geo.eu/>), funded by European Union, are shown. An overview of physical-thermal properties variations under different moisture and load conditions for different mixtures of natural material is presented, based on laboratory and field test data.

Author(s): Eloisa Di Sipio, David Betermann
Organisation: Friedrich-Alexander University
 Erlangen-Nuremberg

